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International Conference on

Green Chemistry and Sustainable Engineering

ABSTRACTSBOOK

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Preface

5th International Conference on Green Chemistry and Sustainable Engineering

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GreenCHEM-22 Welcoming Message

Dear Colleagues,

The **5th International Conference on Green Chemistry and Sustainable Engineering (GreenChem-22)** is organized by academics and researchers belonging to different scientific areas of the University Complutense of Madrid, University Carlos III of Madrid, University of Extremadura, University of las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro, University of Granada, University of Santiago de Compostela, and University of Jaen, with the technical support of **Sciknowledge European Conferences**.

This event aims to create an international forum for academics, researchers and scientists worldwide to discuss worldwide results and proposals regarding the soundest issues related to **Green Chemistry and Sustainable Engineering**.

This event will include the participation of renowned keynote speakers, oral presentations, poster sessions, technical conferences related to the topics dealt with in the Scientific Program, and an attractive social and cultural program.

The papers will be published in the Abstracts E-book of the Conference. Those communications with enough quality can be further considered for publication in International Conference Journals. At the authors' choice, those works unsuitable for publication in any congress journals will be published in the Extended Abstracts E-book.

To finish, I hope that all of you will enjoy the Conference, and I wish our visitors from abroad will have an enjoyable stay in Rome.

Thank you

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Scientific Program

6th International Conference on Green Chemistry and Sustainable Engineering

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GreenCHEM-24 Welcoming Message

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This event aims to create an international forum for academics, researchers and scientists worldwide to discuss worldwide results and proposals regarding the soundest issues related to **Green Chemistry and Sustainable Engineering**.

All accepted papers will be published in the Abstract E-book of the Conference. Those communications considered to have enough quality by authors can be further considered for publication in the International Conference Journals associated with this Conference. This Special Call for Papers Presented at the Congress, and for different Journals, will be sent at the end of the month of September-October. At the authors' choice, those works not suitable for publication in any of the congress journals will be published in the Extended Proceedings E-book of the Congress.

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, I would like to wish all the participants who attend the conference to share their knowledge and establish new research-fruit relationships.

Looking forward to welcoming you in Lisbon!

Yours sincerely,

Prof. José Alcides Peres
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Portugal, UE

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The **Spanish Adsorption Society** in collaboration with **Sciknowledge Education** will award a prize to the best poster communication presented during the congress **6th International Conference on Green Chemistry and Sustainable Engineering (GreenChem-24)** held from July 24th to 26th in Lisbon, Portugal.

The application of plant-based ZnO photocatalysts in the removal of Deoxynivalenol from water utilizing simulated solar irradiation

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1. Introduction – Deoxynivalenol (DON) is the most widespread mycotoxin from the group of trichothecenes [1]. It is produced by molds of the genus *Fusarium*, which are mycological contaminants of cereals worldwide [2]. Acute toxic effects of DON include gastrointestinal complaints, such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and there is also evidence of its immunosuppressive effect [3]. Atmospheric leaching from crops on agricultural land contributes most significantly to the presence of DON in natural waters [4]. This research tends to show the efficiency of the DON removal from deionized water, employing photolysis and photocatalysis under simulated solar irradiation (SSI).

2. Experimental – The influence of two different catalysts, synthesized on the principles of green chemistry, on the degradation efficiency of DON (Biopure, Romer, Austria) was examined. The extract of banana peel (BPE), as well as green tea leaves extract (GTLE) were used for the synthesis of ZnO-based nanoparticles, ZnO BPE and ZnO GTLE. A photoreactor with a xenon lamp (Toption-V, China) was used for degradation experiments, while the treatment efficiency was monitored by high pressure liquid chromatography with a diode array detector (Dionex UltiMate 3000 Series, Thermo Scientific, Germany).

3. Results and Discussion – The results of DON photodegradation efficiency, gathered under various tested conditions, are shown in Image 1. As it can be seen, this mycotoxin is stable during the irradiation utilizing SSI, since only 30% of DON was degraded after 60 min. The application of green catalysts affected different efficiency of DON's degradation. Namely, during photocatalysis using the ZnO BPE catalyst, 38% of DON was degraded after the same timeframe, while the highest degradation activity was achieved in the system with ZnO GTLE catalyst, i.e., 93% of DON was removed, respectively. Even though the photodegradation of DON using UV light is already confirmed [5], our results showed the degradation possibility of DON under SSI, employing the novel plant-based catalysts.

Image 1. Efficiency of direct photolysis and photocatalysis on the DON degradation

4. Conclusions - The newly synthesized green ZnO nanomaterials based on GTLE has shown excellent potential in the photodegradation of the widespread DON mycotoxin. On the other hand, in the case of ZnO BPE, regarding the experimental conditions, further optimization is required to achieve higher photocatalytic activity.

Acknowledgment: This research was supported by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia (Grant No. 7747845, *In situ* pollutants removal from waters by sustainable green nanotechnologies-CleanNanoCatalyze).

5. References

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6th GREENCHEM-24

The Organizing Committee of the **6th International Conference on Green Chemistry and Sustainable Engineering (GreenChem-24)** held in Lisbon, Portugal, from 24th to 26th of July 2024

CERTIFIES

That SANDRA JAKŠIĆ

has presented in the aforesaid Conference as Virtual Poster the Communication entitled

The application of plant-based ZnO photocatalysts in the removal of Deoxynivalenol from water utilizing simulated solar irradiation

Lisbon, 24 July, 2024

Jose Alcides Silvestre Peres

Prof. Jose Alcides Silvestre Peres PhD
GreenChem-24 Chairman
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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

